

Perspectives of the Private High School Teachers on the Modular Distance Learning Modality: A Phenomenology

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Abstract:- This study explores the lived experiences of private high school teachers confronted with the new challenges due to the Covid-19 pandemic. It also seeks to determine the participants' profile in age range by generation, relevant training attended, the highest level of education attained, years in service, and module involvement. The researcher also investigates the participants' problems experienced in work-family conflict, opinions on support by a supervisor, views on distance education, and what had been gained from the experiences. Ten (10) teachers from Buenavista Institute and 20 teachers from Saint James High School participated in the study. The researcher employed purposive sampling and applied statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, and thematic analysis. Findings show that the millennials garnered the highest percentage among the participants, and 50% were trained at the national level. Nineteen (19) out of 30 participants obtained baccalaureate degrees, and in terms of module involvement majority of them were module users and developers. Further probing indicates that a large percentage of the participants claimed to balance work and family life. The supervisor and school heads provided emotional and essential support in meeting the demands of modular distance learning (MDL). In addition, participants viewed distance education as having many flaws and being burdensome, including difficulties in delivering lessons and challenges in conducting the lessons, but they still coped. At the peak of the Covid-19 pandemic, the sudden transition from face-to-face to distance learning caused different implications for teachers' time management, complications in the responsibilities at home and school, and support utilization.

Keywords: MDLM, Work Home Conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic rapidly changed the country's economic stability and educational system. Many teachers in the affected areas of the world suddenly have to prepare their instructional materials, which causes them to spend endless hours creating the modules, to feel frustrated due to potential issues, and to encounter work-family conflicts. With modular instruction, a group of teachers within the

division write self-learning modules (SLMs) distributed to schools. Furthermore, teachers were to develop weekly home learning plans distributed with the SLMs to guide parents to self-paced student learning. As such, this has been a challenging time in the educational system that still calls for teachers, parents, and students to collaborate to achieve quality education. In modular distance learning, the role of the teacher shifted from traditional lecturing in-persons into a remote learning environment. Additionally, teachers must adapt their practices to keep their students engaged in effective and efficient learning as every household has become a classroom.

Considering that most private school teachers are also parents at home, guiding their children in MDLM, it motivates the researcher to take a deeper look into their lived experiences, their perspectives on modular distance learning modality, and the challenges that they encounter along the way. The researcher aims to determine the best coping mechanism and adaptation practices for the teacher during the Covid-19 pandemic.

In Saint James High School and Buenavista Institute, teachers experience many trials towards work. Some have difficulty dealing with time management regarding workloads, online classes, checking modules, monitoring, and giving feedback on students' output. The teachers address students' queries through text messaging, phone calls, messenger chats, and home visitation to provide instructional support. Since most of the teachers are also parents at home, guiding their children in modular distance learning, motivates the researcher to take a deeper look into their lived experiences, their perspectives on modular distance learning and the challenges that they encountered along the way. It is the purpose of the researcher to determine the coping mechanism and adaptations practices by their teachers during the COVID-19 pandemic.

This study aims to determine the perspectives and challenges of private high school teachers in dealing with modular distance learning amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. This study is a way of showcasing a productive way to overcome challenges towards work and family controversy. Then teachers will be ready to know how they would assess and handle these circumstances.

➤ *Statement of the Problem*

This study aimed to provide an in-depth description and understanding of the meaning and value in the lived experiences of the teachers' lived experiences with new challenges due to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Specifically, this qualitative inquiry seeks to answer the following questions:

- What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - ✓ Age range by generation;
 - ✓ Relevant training attended;
 - ✓ Highest educational attainment;
 - ✓ Years in service; and
 - ✓ Module involvement?
- What problems did the participants experience in terms of:
 - ✓ work; and
 - ✓ family?
- What opinions on support from supervisors did participants encounter?
- What are the participants' views on distance education?
- What did the participants gain from the experiences, choices, and challenges?

➤ *Significance of the Study*

This phenomenological study gathers insights from the daily lives of teachers confronted and new challenges due to the Covid-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the research aims to identify the teachers' experiences with work-family-related problems during the pandemic. This study presents the teachers' successes and struggles with modular distance learning modality. Specifically, this shall be useful for the following:

- *Teachers*
The study's results will facilitate a call to address the challenges of teachers facing work-family-related problems during the pandemic and ensure appropriateness and effectiveness in dealing with distance education. It shall help them to employ effective strategies and techniques on how they will face these challenges to maintain quality education.
- *School Administrator*
This will give a practical plan to improve teaching-learning and effectively implement modular distance learning.
- *Aspirant Researchers*
They may use the study's results as a reference or basis for conducting future research related to the present study.
- *Scope and Delimitation of the Study*
This study is a qualitative research conducted with the help of the current professional teachers from Buenavista Institute and Saint James High School S.Y. 2021-2022. There are ten (10) teacher-participants from Buenavista Institute and 20 from Saint James High School.

The profile is limited to the following variables: age range by generation, relevant training attended, highest educational attainment, years in service, and whether they are module users or developers.

As part of the ethical consideration for confidentiality, the names of the participants are held confidential and coded.

This study only covers the lived experiences of teachers who were challenged to combat the teaching-learning process during the COVID-19 pandemic. Lastly, the opinions on support and views of participants on distance education are also taken as important data.

II. METHODS

This study utilizes a qualitative phenomenology research design. The phenomenological study attempts to understand people's experiences with a particular phenomenon. The research study aims to explore the private high school teachers' lived experiences with the modular distance learning modality during the pandemic. Phenomenology focuses on the analysis of conscious and immediate lived experiences and is sensitive to the uniqueness of each person.

➤ *Population and Locale of the Study*

Thirty (30) teachers served as participants in the research study. Ten (10) were from Buenavista Institute, and 20 were from St. James High School. The researcher used a purposive sampling design to determine the participants; they were the educators challenged to perform the teaching-learning process using the MDLM during the COVID-19 pandemic.

➤ *Data Gathering Procedure*

After the research instrument validation, the researcher followed the data-gathering procedure by Creswell (2007).

First, the researcher personally asked for authorization, with a letter containing the purpose of the study, from the principal of Saint James High School and Buenavista Institute.

After granting permission, the researcher conducted an orientation to the participants to inform them about the study and the ethical agreement. After gaining access and establishing rapport with the teachers, the researcher set the interview schedules, then conducted one-on-one interviews with the participants to collect data. The researcher then finalized the total number during the research process, given the principle of data saturation in qualitative research. He then recorded the interview answers and transcribed after.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

➤ *Problem 1*

What is the profile of the participants in terms of their age range by generation, relevant training attended, highest educational attainment, years in service and module involvement?

The Tables below and a graphical illustration indicate the profile of the participants.

Table 1 Frequency and Percent Distribution of Participants' Age Range by Generation, Relevant Training Attended, Years in Service, and Module Involvement

Profile Variables	Category/level	Frequency	Percentage
Age range by generation	Gen Z	10	33.33%
	Millennial	12	40.00%
	Gen X	6	20.00%
	Boomer II	2	6.67%
Total		30	100
Module involvement	user	7	23.33%
	developer	2	6.67%
	user and developer	21	70.00%
Total		30	100

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Profile Variables	Category/level	Frequency	Percentage
Relevant training attended	international	0	0
	national	15	50.00%
	regional	3	10.00%
	division	8	26.67%
	Cluster	1	3.33%
	School	3	10.00%
Total		30	100
Years in service	< 2 yrs	9	30.00%
	3-4 yrs	7	23.33%
	> 4 yrs	14	46.67%
Total		30	100

Table 1 shows the frequency and percent distribution of the Participants' Profiles in terms of age range by generation, relevant training attended, years in service, and module involvement.

The result shows that millennial garnered the highest percentage among the participants having 40% with a corresponding frequency of 12. Next to it is the frequency of ten (10) from Gen Z, with a percentage of 33.33%. A percentage of twenty (20%) corresponds to 6 participants from the level of Gen X. Lastly, Boomer II holds a percentage of 6.67% or a frequency of 2.

The related study by Franisco (2020) found a significant relative contribution of the teacher's academic qualification, content knowledge, instructional quality, evaluation procedures, and job satisfaction to the students' academic performance. Also, another study revealed that the attributes of a teacher affect their skills. In particular, teachers' instructional practices affect students' academic

performance. As a result, principals of schools and education administrators encountered a brand different set of challenges. Boomers are veteran teachers with the experience and ability to cope with new changes in 21st-century demands as required by the K12. Furthermore, veteran teachers may not have the expertise to use technology in the classroom, but they have the expertise to utilize specific 21st-century skills earned from years of experience.

Hence, generation differences in chronological age are not a hindrance to implementing educational innovations and the teaching and learning skills that support 21st-century expectations (Alufohai, P. & Ibhafidon, H., 2015).

The young individuals repeatedly referred to as "Generation Z" will bring a brand different set of habits, expectations, and life experiences into the classroom. So as a result, principals of schools and education administrators encountered a brand different set of challenges. Boomers are

veteran teachers with the experience and ability to cope with new changes in 21st-century demands as the K12 requires. Furthermore, veteran teachers may not have the expertise to use technology in the classroom, but they have the expertise to utilize certain 21st-century skills earned from years of experience. Hence, generation differences in chronological age are not a hindrance to implementing educational innovations and the teaching and learning skills that support 21st-century expectations (Alufohai, P. & Ibhafidon, H., 2015).

Regarding relevant training attended, results show that out of 30 respondents, only 15 or 50% have training at the national level. Furthermore, 26.67% or 8 participants have attended under the division level category. At the cluster level, only one (1) or 3.33 % of the 30 participants have it. None have been in international training.

In-service teachers’ training is one of the ways to address the presence of students with very different needs in the classrooms. This presents those teachers with a higher level of training and gives a big help to every individual. When teachers possess good quality in their teaching career and focus on the needs of every individual, this may lead to higher education for students and teachers’ improvements.

In the module involvement, the group that gathered the highest mark was the user and developer, with a percentage of 70% and a frequency of 21. This is seconded by seven (7) participants, or 23.33% among user categories. The least percentage yielded two (2) developers’ categories, or 6.67%.

The study’s results show that teaching materials are effective implementation tools for learning materials in

distance class lessons. The MDL modality utilized by the participants in their lessons indicated that the module users were also developers. This batch of teachers is the participant in this study.

The materials here include all the tools teachers need to make learning more interesting and memorable. Teaching materials are a strategic element for teachers because they help elaborate the lessons physically given. A concept that teachers could not have achieved without teaching materials is embedded in the teachers’ quest for quality education. It allows students to study more comfortably and will positively impact their academic achievement or performance (Oni, 2020).

Results also indicated that 14 participants, or 46.67%, have been in service for more than four (4) years. Seven (7) among the 30 participants, or 23.33%, have been in service for between 3-4 years, and nine (9), or 30%, have served less than two (2) years in teaching.

Those teachers with years of experience in the profession turned out to develop more students with a higher academic performance that teachers need to improve and have more experience in the teaching profession. Some evidence suggests that teachers who remain to teach after three (3) years are less effective on average than those who leave (Clotfelter et al., 2016). However, other research has found that less effective teachers are more likely to transfer and leave teaching (Boyd et al., 2019).

In terms of educational attainment, the figure below indicates the frequency distribution.

Fig 1 Graphical Presentation of the Frequency Distribution of the Participants' Educational Attainment

Figure 1 shows the frequency distribution of the participant’s educational attainment. As shown, 19 out of the 30 participants are from the college category. Followed by the college with MA units are six (6) participants. The MA degree holder exhibits a frequency of four (4), and a very low frequency of one (1) has the Doctoral units.

Wenglisky (2020) suggested that a teacher’s qualification cannot only be determined by just checking his or her educational level. A teacher must have these things and be fully equipped for higher and good quality education to be effective in her/his field. It depends on the teacher to help students be knowledgeable and active. The teacher plays a vital role in the teaching-learning process.

➤ *Problem 2*

What problems did the participants experience in terms of work and family?

The table below summarizes the participants’ problems experienced that are related to work and family while working during the pandemic.

Table 2 Thematic Analysis of Participants' Work-Related Problems Experienced During the Pandemic

Participants	Codes	Category	Themes	Descriptions
BI 3	Time management	Time-based	Work related problem	Inadequacy of time in facing the new normal education has strained the participants and created varied responses on their behavior in performing the continuity of education under pandemic time.
SJHS 6	Lack of time			
BI 1	Inadequate time w/family			
SJHS 7	Juggling time with work /family	Strain-based	Work related problem	Inadequacy of time in facing the new normal education has strained the participants and created varied responses on their behavior in performing the continuity of education under pandemic time.
BI 5	Longer working hours			
SJHS 5	Commitment w/ work	Behavioral dimension	Work related problem	Inadequacy of time in facing the new normal education has strained the participants and created varied responses on their behavior in performing the continuity of education under pandemic time.
BI 9	Demand for leisure			
SJHS 2	Can't do household chores			
SJHS 1	Exhausted at school			

Table 2 shows the views of participants on work-related problems. Time is essential in the work of teachers experiencing problems during the pandemic. The time-based, strain-based conflict and behavioral dimensions are the categorized data gathered from interviews conducted with 30 participants.

There are three themes present in the interview in terms of the work-related problem.

The time for schoolwork affects the time for housework. Home is the new environment at work, so managing time between school works affects household chores.

Challenges have been imposed on modular distance learning, such as preparing and distributing modules, monitoring students’ learning, and checking and evaluating modules. Workloads lead to stress that they are required to do at home.

Since teachers were adjusting to modular distance learning, teachers experienced work-life imbalance. The workloads affect the quality of time with family. They lose their time doing tasks at school.

Findings have indicated several variables expressed in codes why the teachers can experience work-related problems. Schoolwork and workloads affect family life. Time management is one area where COVID-19 has caused significant challenges in school, although these difficulties vary individually and manifest differently for everyone. Due

to the pandemic's impacts, faculty and students have had to change their schedules. Both groups face significant difficulties, especially those transforming typical daytime face-to-face courses into modular learning modalities (Heath & Shine, 2021).

Below are some of the participants’ expressed views regarding work-related problems.

“ There are times that I get exhausted at school and that makes me lose time to bond after. There are instances where I don’t get to join them in the table to eat dinner.” (SJHS 1).

“ Teachers commonly faced lack or time to their family because of their heavy loads in school. And it leads to work family conflict since most of the time teachers works overtime such as paper works and rush grades and bringing their school activities/ paper works to home.” (SJHS 6).

“ In my experience, the only conflict I had was the time management I had to juggle with my work and family. Currently, I am the head of the household, so once I get home, I won’t do school work stuff but if necessary, I should make time to balance it.” (SJHS 7).

“ When in terms of work family conflict as a teacher one of the problems. I experienced the lack of time management. When I do work sometimes I neglect my responsibilities at home.” (BI 1).

Table 3 Thematic Analysis of Participants' Family-Related Problems Experienced During the Pandemic

Participants	Codes	Category	Themes	Descriptions
BI 7	Financial problem	Financial issues	Family related problem	Problems experienced by the participants related to family related problem have disrupted their mental wellness and shaken their behavioral dimensions. Added to it are the financial problems as well as personal problems heightened during this pandemic time.
BI 5	Feeling guilt			
SJHS 16	Tension/Pressured			
BI 9	Stress	Mental wellness		
SJHS 2	Stress and pressured			
SJHS 10	Less focus in teaching			
SJHS 5	Commitment	Behavioral dimension		
SJHS 4	Can't go to family events			
BI 4	Personal problem			

Table 3 summarizes the family-related problems. The financial issues and mental wellness consisted of financial problems, guilt, tension or pressure, stress, and less focus on teaching. The behavioral dimension included commitment, inability to attend family events, and personal problems.

Family problems affect the quality of teaching. Family problems involve financial difficulties. With this, teachers fail to accomplish their duties and obligations of teachers. They have a hard time adjusting, which affects the quality of teaching.

Teachers have been mentally exhausted in balancing work and family life. The private school teachers encountered conflicts between work and family. They could not manage their time between work and family because their work environment was home. So, work-related demands interfere with home responsibilities. For instance, teachers must finish their workloads even if it is not the working hours. In addition, family responsibilities impede work-related activities.

Teachers have also experienced financial stress in meeting the demands of the family. The salary offered in private schools is around 12,000-15,000 (Marquez, 2017). During the pandemic, the closure of establishments affects every Filipino because they have to stop working. With this, private school teachers feel the financial stress during modular distance learning, especially if they are breadwinners who must sustain the family's needs.

During the pandemic, working from home is an alternative working arrangement, particularly for teachers. Based on the results, this setup is difficult for teachers to balance work and family. It affects the teaching quality and even mental health. Brennan (2021) stated that any employment could contribute to depression based on the surroundings and level of support offered. Job insecurity, a

lack of work-life balance, a hostile work environment, and overworking are some of the most prevalent factors that contribute to depression in those who are employed.

Below are some of the participants' expressed views regarding work-related problems.

“ Financially Pressured. When you're the bread winner in your family, you can't deny the fact that you can feel pressure specially if the salary cannot meet the demand of your family.” (SJHS 11).

“Increased job duties as a result of bulk modules to distribute and retrieve would have a significant impact on the family work conflict. When it comes to checking the students work more time spent working means less time with the family.” (SJHS 15).

“ There was a time that I've been working at home and that time I was sick. I have a niece and she is 3 years old. People at our house that time is so busy and I have no choice but I have to watch after her. I've experience it once while teaching my online students. I am also watching after my niece which was a problem because I can't really focus on my students because my niece needs attention.” (SJHS 16).

“ Emergency, family and financial problems from family sometimes it could create unfocused to work and not functional in terms of teaching responsibilities..” (BI 2).

“ Some of my duties and obligations were not totally accomplished caused by family problems such as emergency situations and personal problems.” (BI 4).

“Family problem/Personal problem because I have a lot of time to my work than to my family this is my problem based on my experienced as a teacher.” (BI 8).

Fig 2 Thematic Mapping of Work-Family Conflict

On the participants' lived experiences, the thematic mapping summarizes the deductive approach of the thematic analysis. Of the identified themes of the family/work-related problems. As shown, many respondents claim to be able to manage their time with work and family; thus, they claim to have not experienced work/family problems. It is because they are single and do not have their own family loaded with responsibilities with children and /or house chores or school matters.

➤ *Problem 3*

What opinions on support from supervisors did participants encounter?

Table 4 Thematic Analysis on Supervisors' Support for the Participants during the Pandemic

Participants	Codes	Category	Themes	Descriptions
BI 4	on line Seminar	Professional growth	Academic advancement	It can be seen that during the implementation of distance education, participants have the usual support in the advancement of their profession. Emotional and essential supports are also manifested
BI 1	Professional Encouragement			
BI 5	Seminars			
SJHS 13	Gives considerations	Emotional support	Self - endurance	
SJHS 11	Gives motivation			
SJHS 7	Stress recognition			
BI 9	Emotional support to working mom			
SJHS 1	Load allowance	Essential support	Health and wellness	
SJHS 3	Health and safety issues			

Table 4 shows the supervisors' or school management heads' provided support, such as emotional and essential support in meeting the demands of distance education. Results show that some teachers have experienced limited support, as illustrated in their responses of some having insufficient facilities and management.

Reskilling and upskilling teachers through webinars and seminars will help teachers adjust to distance learning. Specifically, the teachers must learn the transition from

traditional classroom management to digital integration skills.

Supervisors develop coping mechanisms to reduce stress, such as giving consideration, especially when submitting papers. In addition, giving motivation and stress recognition are essential to help teachers to adjust. The emotional support given by the teachers promotes well-being. Through this, it will lessen the burnout of teachers.

Work resources to support teachers in the teaching-learning process. Aside from emotional support, load

allowances and other resources given by the supervisors are a big help in sustaining the needs of teachers in teaching. Since private school teachers are financial stress, this work resources support will lessen the burden on teachers.

Distance education has been implemented as the immediate solution to follow DepEd Order 012 Series 2020 to continue education amidst the pandemic. Thus, supporting teachers in this endeavor is essential to maintain their effectiveness. Based on the results, supervisors support their teachers through professional development, motivation to cope, and instructional resources. Predergast & French (2022) stated that school administrators should consider these three effective techniques to let their teachers know they are cherished, respected, and acknowledged as they seek to improve the working environment. So, they are essential in providing a working environment where teachers thrive and stay. Moreover, school administrators or supervisors need to invest in the professional development of teachers. To provide quality and skilled teachers, they have to conduct or provide training and seminars.

Below are some of the expressed participants' views regarding supervisor support:

"I can say that we have enough support from our supervisor/administration when it comes to teachers aid like load allowance and internet connection at school." (SJHS 1).

"Our school offered seminars & workshops (online) where teachers could participate and learn more even if the modality itself is new." (SJHS 8).

"Motivational support was necessary during the emergence of the pandemic, and I think this was well provided by the supervisor of the school where I'm currently working. Although, there wasn't amplification on financial support, but it was understandable since private institutions have to look on it's financial stability if it can withstand it may face on the economic crises." (SJHS 11).

"The principal focus on helping and engaging teachers to distance education. To help improve teaches professional development from new modality of teaching." (BI 1).

"Our principal give us seminars (online) for us to be prepared during modular modality." (BI 5).

"There are allowances that has been provided by the teachers and other support like spiritual, mental and physical support that the institution provided." (BI 7).

➤ **Problem 4**

What are the participants' views on distance education?

Table 5 Thematic Analysis of the Participants' Views on Distance Education/MDL

Participants	Codes	Category	Theme	Descriptions
SJHS 1	Difficulty in delivery of lessons	Diversified contributions of independence	Gaps in teaching learning-process	As experienced by the participants, distance education is quite difficult, burdensome and has lots of flaws and still coping to such challenges.
BI 9	Challenging in conducting the lessons			
SJHS 15	Still coping	Values re-invented	Integration of ICT is quite challenging for teachers	
SJHS 13	Lots of flaws			
SJHS 19	burdensome			
SJHS 4	Inclusive learning		Commitment of parents and students for the effectiveness of distance learning	

Table 5 presents the participants' views on distance education, including difficulties in delivering lessons, challenges in conducting the lessons, still coping, lots of flaws, burdensome, and inclusive learning.

Gaps in the teaching-learning process. Modular distance learning encountered learning gaps among students. Teachers have no assurance if the students do the activities on their own. So, learners may have missed a skill or competency.

Integration of ICT is quite challenging for teachers. It is difficult to adjust to the transition from the traditional classroom to the integration of technology. Teachers and students have to use technology to interact with each other. This innovation, integrating ICT, is challenging, especially for older teachers.

To make distance learning effective, the commitment of parents and students toward learning is essential. Students have to learn at home, and the role of the parents is to

support and teach the learners. Parents directly impact the education their students receive, especially in an online learning setting.

Three themes were revealed in the interview of the participants. First, there are still gaps in the teaching-learning process, including the reliability of students' learning since students are independent in technology. Second, the integration of ICT, especially for the boomer teachers are challenging. Lastly, the effectiveness of distance learning depends on the cooperation of parents and students. Dumanon et al. (2022) revealed that the Saint Michael College of Caraga teachers are concerned about the students' academic progress and the parents'/guardians' support over the delay in passing the Learning Modules. There are often delays in submitting the learning modules because the teachers know that the parents and guardians cannot fully meet their pupils' learning demands. It was advised that management and teachers improve their tracking and monitoring of students' progress. Bring back home visits, hold parent-teacher-school counselor conferences, and practice the referral process by holding some meetings with the students' and parents' parents. Additionally, implement a program to continuously engage the teachers in additional training and teaching techniques throughout these modular learning modalities. Regarding distance education/MDL, the participants expressed mixed emotions and varied ideas about distance education. However, according to some authorities, distance education can provide access to students in rural areas but could be stressful for students with less college experience and self-confidence (Menlove, Hansford, & Lignugaris-Kraft, 2003).

The implementation of distance education has been made as the immediate solution to follow DepEd Order 012 Series 2020 in order to continue education amidst the pandemic. Thus, in areas where internet connection is impossible, MDL modality is their option at hand. This implies that without much preparation by the schools and teachers, the challenge of the teaching-learning process is now put to the test. Hence, most participants view distance education as a challenging endeavor with which most are coping.

Below are some of the participants' expressed views regarding distance learning education:

“For me, distance education is very vital in the educational system since it provides inclusive learning for all students even how far they are from the school.” (SJHS 4).

“Frankly, I am not a fan of the distance education, looking at the status quo, this modality has gradually deteriorating the level of learning that students get from the usual face to face classes. And current studies suggest, it is ineffective to the retention of the students.” (SJHS 11).

“Distance education has lots of flaws because of too much learner independent learning where they have the freedom to only rely on the use of internet when answering and worst is the tendency of cheating will skyrocket hence there will be no learning or their learning will be compromised.” (SJHS 14).

“I fell adapt at integrating technology into our typical face to face teaching. Very challenging in part of us teachers..” (BI 9).

“In this time of pandemic, we only have one option and that is distance learning. Distance education is only effective if there is a cooperation of the students and parents. No matter how hard the teachers try in making modules like crafting and likewise, it all boils down to the idea of discipline and responsible action of the learners.” (BI 10).

➤ **Problem 5**

What did the participants gain from the experiences, choices, and challenges?

Figure 3 presents the concept map gained from the experiences and challenges of private teachers in modular distance learning. At the peak of the Covid-19 pandemic, the sudden transition from face-to-face to distance learning causes different implications for teachers, including time management, complications in the responsibilities at home and school, and utilizing support for teachers. This implication affects the quality of the teaching-learning process and effective distance learning.

Fig 3 Concept Mapping on the Teachers' Experiences, Choices, and Challenges

The closure of schools due to the Covid-19 pandemic resulted in the emergent transition from face-to-face to distance learning. Lemay et al., (2019) stated that teaching and learning activities had been moved in response to the new pandemic reality that has afflicted. This affects daily life, work life, and even the education system.

Participants had difficulty balancing tasks in the family and as a teacher. It affects the mental health and well-being of teachers. The health and well-being of teachers are negatively impacted by excessive stress levels, leading to teacher burnout, low engagement, job discontent, subpar performance, and some of the most significant rates ever (Pennsylvania State University, 2016). Hence, it causes negative consequences for teachers that result in the quality of the teaching process.

Moreover, they have struggled with their work responsibilities in their home lives during the pandemic. It is quite challenging since the working environment has also transformed. This also causes stress and pressure to the teachers. Mandapat & Farin (2021) revealed the work-from-home arrangements, which include job-related items and responsibilities, professional development and promotion opportunities, recognition and work achievement, organizational policy and administration and technical supervision, working relations and compensation benefits, and physical working conditions and health issues were found to be difficult.

However, supervisors provide emotional and resource support to reduce stress and improve well-being. These supports lessen the burdens of teachers in their work and family problems. Prendergast & French (2022) stated that school administrators consider the three effective techniques to let the teachers know they are cherished, respected, and acknowledged as they seek to improve the working environment.

The domino effect of these challenges can affect the quality of teaching and effectivity of distance learning since there are still gaps in transitioning. The domino effect can weaken the educational system. So, if the teachers are unprepared in the transition to distance learning, it will affect their teaching performance. This will consider a cause for ineffective distance learning. UPCEA (2021) stated that each state utilized a different K-12 public education strategy in the chaos brought on by COVID-19: some reinstated in-person classes, some adopted a hybrid system, and some persisted with distant learning. More than 12 million K-12 children were underserved regarding internet access at the beginning of 2021 (UPCEA,2021). Hence, it decreases education quality and engagement.

IV. CONCLUSION

Participants are aware of the usage of ICT and showed dependency on technologies since most participants were Generation Z and Millennials. Moreover, they are also equipped with training. So, they have knowledge, skills, and competence in using distance learning. However, they still experience challenges or problems.

Teachers have encountered challenges in implementing modular distance learning in terms of work and family-related problems. This research concludes that modular distance learning affects mental health, including time management, stress, and pressure in balancing work life and family.

Emotional and resources support from supervisors can lessen the burden of teachers during modular distance learning.

There are still areas for improvement and gaps in implementing modular distance learning that causes challenges to the teachers. So, a domino effect happened in the teaching quality because of the challenges experienced by the teachers.

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